

DIPLOMA

TA'LIM FIDOYILARI

RESPUBLIKA ILMIY JURNALIDA

Akramov Muhammadjon

**THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF CORPORATE GOVERNANCE IN PROTECTING
THE RIGHTS OF CONSUMERS IN THE FIELD OF ELECTRONIC COMMERCE**

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